

Information sheet 2.02

Laboratory testing

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

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A. Description of the RRO

Tests, defined as "official examination, other than visual, to determine if pests are present or to identify pests" (ISPM 5), may be included in diagnostic protocols for regulated pests (ISPM 27). In diagnostic protocols, pest detection is distinguished from pest identification. Tests may be implemented at both stages. For example, biochemical or molecular assays, like ELISA tests or culturing on selective media, may be performed to detect a pest but they may also be used for pest identification.

Diagnostic protocols describe the minimum requirements for reliable diagnosis of regulated pests. This may be achieved by a single method or a combination of methods based on different principles, as it is for example required in the current legislation for potato diseases caused by bacteria (Council Directive 98/57/EC of 20 July 1998 on the control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi et al ; Council Directive 93/85/EEC of 4 October 1993 on the control of potato ring rot). The methods included in diagnostic protocols must be selected on the basis of their sensitivity, specificity and reproducibility (ISPM 27). However, in circumstances such as routine diagnosis or surveillance, speed and costs may be more critical than the level of analytical sensitivity or specificity (PM7/76). In other cases a longer time may be taken to issue a result, as a wider number of less sensitive analyses may be more efficient in practice than a smaller number of more performant analyses. Methods for quick preliminary indications of identity (which will later need to be confirmed) may also be included in diagnostic protocols.

Tests can be based on (bio-)chemical (including serological, molecular, biochemical, olfactory, etc.), physical (including acoustic, thermal, microscopy, etc.) and biological (indexing, growing in selective media, etc.) methods, and can depend on morphological and morphometric characteristics, biological properties such as virulence or host range of a pest, and on biochemical and molecular properties. Culturing and/or isolation may be required for morphological identification or biochemical and molecular assays (ISPM 27). Pest specific examples of laboratory diagnostic protocols can be found in the series PM 7 of EPPO Standards on Diagnostics, as well as in the annexes of ISPM 27.

Tests can be carried out not only on plants or other commodities, but also in pest vectors captured in the environment giving in this last case information on the presence of the pest in the place of production.

Since tests and other elements of the diagnostic protocol are performed on a sample of plants or other materials, the significance of the test results is highly dependent on the sampling technique, which is described in RRO 2.03.

B. Risk factors

As a supporting measure, testing does not have any direct effect on the risk factors addressed in a risk assessment but, depending on the organism(s) to be controlled, its execution is indispensable for completion of other RROs or combination of RROs: pest free area, pest free production place, pest free consignment, certification of plant reproductive material (voluntary/official), delimitation of buffer zones, phytosanitary certificate/plant passport, certified and approved premises, pest free plants for planting, use of non-contaminated water, post-entry quarantine.

The current regulatory frame (Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8 May 2000 on Protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community) includes specific requirements of testing for the presence of arthropods, nematodes, fungi, bacteria, viruses and phytoplasmas on a wide range of plants species, targeting in particular the reproductive material.

Points where testing may be combined with other RRO		In area of production	On crops at place of production	Pre-harvest treatment	Post-harvest	At import	At place of destination
Combined with RROs	pest free area	x	x				
	pest free production place		x				
	pest free consignment				x		
	certification of plant reproductive material	x	x		x		x
	delimitation of buffer zones	x	x				
	phytosanitary certificate/plant passport	x	x	x	x		
	certified and approved premises	x	x				
	pest free plants for planting		x	x	x	x	x
	use of non-contaminated water	x	x				
	post-entry quarantine					x	x

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

The effectiveness of a test to determine the presence of a pest and/or its identity is characterized by its specificity (detection of a given species and not others), sensitivity (ability to detect low population levels, i.e., early infections/infestations) and reproducibility (repetition of analyses of the same material leading to similar results). The results from the test are also indirectly influenced by the accuracy of the sampling process (size of samples, appropriateness of the selection of items to be sampled).

Few, if any, tests are thought to be perfectly sensitive and specific (Venette et al., 2002). To minimise the possibilities of false positive results, two separate assays based on different principles can be used in parallel. For example, following a positive serological screening test, results can be confirmed by isolating and identifying the causal organism or by rapid screening tests based on DNA technology (e.g. ring rot bacteria in potatoes) (van der Wolf et al., 2005). Test reproducibility is influenced by both technical performance and assay performance characteristics (a test may demonstrate appropriate process control but poor diagnostic performance or vice versa). If the validity of the test results is questioned, it is important to be able to distinguish between the two (PM 7/84).

Factors determining the effectiveness of tests include (PM7/84):

- Personnel (training)
- location
- environmental conditions during sample storage and test performance
- diagnostic methods
- equipment
- reference materials/cultures
- sampling
- sample handling

Diagnostic tests may not only differ in effectiveness but also in levels of time necessary to issue a result and costs, which are factors to be taken into account when deciding in the most effective test or combination of tests for a specific circumstance. Test specificity is particularly important for tests in diagnostic protocols for regulated pests, because phytosanitary actions may be based on these results (PM7/76).

The different types of tests have specific particularities that can affect their outcome. As illustrative examples, in PCR analyses, some primers can induce dimers or unspecific bands. Also sequence homologies to chloroplasts and plastids increase the risk of false positives (Heinrich et al. 2001). Another problem with PCR detection is the presence of putative inhibitors in pest, plant or soil materials that lead to false negative results (Heinrich et al. 2001; van der Wolf et al. 2005). In serological tests, the occurrence of non-specific serological reactions can lead to false-positives (van der Wolf et al., 2005). In the case of fungus spores, the sieve size is a key factor in the effectiveness of their detection and identification (Tan and Wright 2009).

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

The application of this supporting RRO requires specific facilities. Diagnostic laboratories should be such as to enable a correct performance of the diagnosis. The laboratory should be appropriately equipped to ensure proper storage, diagnosis and containment of samples (PM7/84). Another technical difficulty in the implementation of some diagnostic tests is the unavailability of antisera or specific primers for specific organisms (Heinrich et al. 2001). In relation to pest isolation, pathogens may grow slowly and be notoriously difficult to isolate on artificial growing media (e.g. ring rot bacteria in potatoes). This problem can be overcome by bioassays *in planta* (van der Wolf et al., 2005) or using pure cell cultures. However, long timescales associated with these tests are an inconvenient bottleneck in diagnostic tests (van der Wolf et al., 2005).

The implementation of this RRO implies several costs, including the cost of chemicals and consumables (laboratory consumables, chemicals, enzymes, glass wares, plastic disposables, etc) required for the

different analyses and procedures, labour (personnel, including training) and time requirements, costs of buildings and equipment used, as well as overhead costs such as power, heating and cooling (Tan and Wright, 2009).

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

For many arthropods and parasitic plants, the inspections carried out in the fields, on pests captured by traps or on the commodities may lead to same results than testing allowing the identification of the pest by visual observation.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

Surveillance (Gonzalez and Troncoso, 2007)
 Eradication (Gonzalez and Troncoso, 2007)
 Phytosanitary certification (Saldarelli et al., 1996)
 Visual inspections (Gu et al., 2006; FAO 2006)

See also under B. Risk factors.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO.

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combinations
Samples from plants, soils or any other material	Laboratory or other controlled environment	Detection and/or identification of a pest	Establishment of required conditions to perform the test; availability of equipment and materials; skilled personnel	Similar results obtained with Inspection but this is limited to pests with characteristic unique symptoms. Laboratory testing is often combined with inspection in a tiered approach to detection and identification. This approach can be part of a diagnostic protocol. Laboratory testing may be combined with many other RROs.

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